

Recent Trends in the Surgical Treatment of Idiopathic Intracranial Hypertension: A Systematic Review

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Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH) is a complex neurological condition with multifactorial origins, predominantly affecting obese women of reproductive age. This systematic review aims to explore recent trends in the surgical treatment of idiopathic intracranial hypertension.

Methods: This systematic review was conducted according to guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA). The literature search encompassed an extensive database including PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane library. Studies published from 2014-2024 were included in the analysis. The quality of the included studies was evaluated using the proper tools suited to the study design. The synthesis and analysis of data included a summary of study characteristics, aims and objectives, surgical technique, and main study results/conclusions.

Results: Sample sizes in the selected studies ranged from 7 to 46,065 participants. The most common surgical techniques used for idiopathic intracranial hypertension were venous sinus stenting (VSS), CSF Diversion: Lumboperitoneal (LP) shunting and ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunting, lumbopleural shunting, bariatric surgery and optic nerve sheath fenestration (ONSF). Generally, the studies discovered the increasing trends in venous sinus stenting procedures in the management of IIH and emphasised bariatric surgery's effectiveness over community weight management interventions in lowering intracranial pressure and aiding weight loss. Overall, these studies present a diverse range of treatment approaches, with a focus on efficiency and outcomes in managing IIH.

Conclusion: This systematic review concludes that various surgical techniques, such as VP shunting, LP shunting with programmable valves, ONSF, venous sinus stenting and bariatric surgery are helpful in the management of IIH. Venous sinus stenting emerges as a promising surgical intervention for medically refractory IIH, offering substantial symptomatic relief with minimal risks.

Keywords: Idiopathic intracranial hypertension, venous sinus stenting, lumboperitoneal shunting, ventriculoperitoneal shunting, lumbopleural shunting, bariatric surgery, optic nerve sheath fenestration.

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Introduction

Idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH), also known as pseudotumor cerebri, is a complex neurological condition with multifactorial origins, predominantly affecting obese women of reproductive age [1]. The precise mechanism remains unclear, but involves dysregulation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamics and potential metabolic/hormonal influences [2].

The pathophysiology of IIH remains controversial. Elevated intracranial pressure in idiopathic intracranial hypertension is considered the result of a dysregulation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamics, through excessive secretion, reduced drainage, or both. The pathophysiology likely involves a combination of mechanisms [1,2,3], in-

cluding: dysregulation of CSF dynamics, changes in venous sinus pressure and potential metabolic and hormonal factors. Key symptoms include headache, vision loss, pulsatile tinnitus, papilloedema and potential cognitive dysfunction [1,4].

Diagnostic approach involves clinical evaluation, neurological examination, imaging studies (MRI, MR venography), measurement of intracranial pressure and ruling out secondary causes [1].

Treatment aims to alleviate symptoms and prevent permanent vision loss, with ongoing research seeking more targeted therapeutic approaches [1,2].

The most effective treatments for Idiopathic Intracranial Hypertension (IIH) include:

Medical treatments: Acetazolamide is considered first-line medical therapy that reduces cerebrospinal fluid production, typically started at 500 mg twice daily, can be increased up to 3-4 g daily and it is more effective when combined with weight loss [5,6,7]. Alternative medications include topiramate and furosemide which can be used for patients intolerant to primary medications [5].

Emerging surgical approaches include Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) diversion (ventriculoperitoneal or lumboperitoneal shunt), Optic Nerve Sheath Fenestration (ONSF), neurovascular stenting, Venous Sinus Stenting (VSS) and bariatric surgery. Venous Sinus Stenting (VSS) is a minimally invasive technique having less complication risk, provides immediate relief for symptoms like pulsatile tinnitus and can resolve vision issues within three months.

The primary treatment goals are reducing intracranial pressure, preserving vision, and alleviating symptoms. Idiopathic Intracranial Hypertension (IIH) represents a complex neurological disorder where the primary treatment goal is to preserve optic nerve function and manage increased intracranial pressure [3]. Recent surgical management strategies have evolved significantly, offering multiple interventional approaches for patients with medically refractory conditions [7].

Shunting procedures have become substantially more prevalent compared to alternative surgical methods [8]. Between 2010 and 2016, approximately 10,423 shunt procedures were performed for Pseudotumor Cerebri Syndrome (PTCS) [8]. Surgical interventions predominantly target women, with 92.4% of procedures performed in female patients [8]. Notably, neurovascular stenting remains uncommon due to limited clinical evidence and lack of consensus regarding patient selection [9]. The surgical decision-making process emphasizes a personalized, case-by-case approach, considering individual patient characteristics and specific clinical presentations [7].

The use of bariatric surgery represents a striking advancement in IIH management. Bariatric surgery is beneficial for morbidly obese patients, helps to reduce intracranial pressure and potential to achieve significant weight loss (up to 24% body weight) [7]. Lifestyle management is important in managing IIH, weight loss of 5-10% can yield significant symptom relief, incorporation of low-sodium diet and regular exercise strongly advocated [10]. These emerging trends underscore the dynamic nature of surgical interventions in IIH management, highlighting the importance of continued research and personalized treatment strategies. The present systematic review aims to explore recent trends in the surgical treatment of idiopathic intracranial hypertension.

Method

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This systematic review was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guideline [11]. We only included studies that focused on the surgical treatment of idiopathic intracranial hypertension.

Search Strategy

To identify relevant studies, we searched PubMed, Science Direct and Cochrane library databases using the following keywords and their derivatives: idiopathic intracranial hypertension, pseudotumor cerebri, and surgical treatment. Searches on databases were done by employing the Boolean Logic (AND, OR and NOT) to generate different combinations of search strings. After the identification of relevant studies duplicates were removed. Manual searches of reference list of included articles were performed to search for possible studies not captured by the electronic searches. The title and abstract were screened for eligibility. Finally, the full text research articles were assessed to verify whether the study met the inclusion criteria.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Surgical treatment for idiopathic intracranial hypertension
- Adult patients (≥ 16 years)
- Full text available
- Published in English
- Clinical trials
- Observational studies
- Retrospective studies

Exclusion criteria

- Paediatric patients
- Studies conducted on animals
- Studies published in languages other than English
- Case studies
- Commentaries, editorials and short communications
- Abstracts
- Literature reviews
- Systematic reviews and meta-analyses

Studies published from 2014-2024 were included in this systematic review which assessed different types of surgical treatment of idiopathic intracranial hypertension. A pre-screening or pilot literature review was meticulously conducted to ensure the reliability and credibility of the literature selection process. This pre-screening was performed by two independent researchers, and discrepancies were settled by a third reviewer. Title and abstract of each study were thoroughly examined to ascertain its relevance to the research objectives.

Data extraction and synthesis was performed after appropriate screening of the studies based on the

inclusion and exclusion criteria. The extracted data included publication year, country, study design, sample size, aims and objectives, surgical technique, and main study results/conclusions. The collected data were presented as findings of this systematic review after analysis.

Result

Initial search identified 3855 studies from the databases and other sources. 3590 records were

screened after initial exclusion of the studies. Following an assessment of the titles and abstracts, 34 articles were selected for further consideration. Following that, 6 studies were eliminated based on the inclusion criteria. We screened 28 studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Finally, we selected 13 studies because of non-availability of some data in the other studies. The process of selection of the studies is depicted in the PRISMA study selection diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Chart

Table 1: Salient features of the included studies

Author, Publication year	Country	Design of the study	Sample size	Aim	Technique	Outcome/Result	Conclusion
Menger RP et al. 2014 [12]	US	Comparative study	4480	To compare the complication rates and health care charges between lumbo-peritoneal (LP) shunting versus ventriculo-peritoneal (VP) shunting	CSF Diversion: Lumbo-peritoneal (LP) shunting and ventriculo-peritoneal (VP) shunting.	Mean hospital length of stay (LOS) significantly differed between primary VP (3 days) and primary LP shunt procedures (4 days).	In idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH), VP shunt placement is superior to LP shunting with clinical outcomes related to hospital length of stay, death, and

							revision surgery.
Alkherayf F et al. 2015 [13]	Canada	Retro-spective study	7	To evaluate the clinical outcomes and complications rate among IIH patients who underwent lumboperitoneal (LP) shunt insertion with a programmable Strata valve.	Lumboperitoneal (LP) shunt insertion and programmable Strata valve.	The mean opening pressure was 35.8 cm H ₂ O. The initial valve setting was 1.5, and four patients required post-operative valve pressure adjustment. All patients showed significant improvement in objective visual testing at follow-up and less frequent headaches.	LP shunts with programmable Strata valve systems are a potential alternative to conventional LP and programmable ventriculoperitoneal shunt systems as well as optic nerve sheath fenestration.
Obi EE et al. 2015 [14]	United Kingdom	Retro-spective study	14	To determine visual outcomes of IIH patients, who underwent optic nerve sheath fenestration (ONSF).	optic nerve sheath fenestration (ONSF)	ONSF resulted in statistically significant improvement/stabilisation in visual acuity, visual fields and colour vision.	ONSF is a safe procedure which stabilises visual function in majority of maximally medicated patients but also offers improved visual function to some patients.
Alkoshahm et al. 2016 [15]	Egypt	Clinical trial	12	to evaluate the lumbopleural shunting as an alternative technique to LP shunts.	lumbopleural shunting	Mean cerebrospinal fluid opening pressures was 37 cmH ₂ O. The mean operative time was 42.5 minutes.	LP shunt is a potentially effective technique in terms of symptoms control and vision improvement in treatment of IIH.
Shields LBE et al. 2019 [16]	US	Retro-spective study	110	To investigate the long-term outcomes of venous sinus stenting in a large group of patients with IIH.	Venous sinus stenting	Poststenting, 74% resolution of papilledema and 43% complete resolution of headaches.	Venous sinus stenting is a safe and effective means of treating IIH.
Liu X et al. 2019 [17]	China	Retro-spective study	88	To evaluate the effects of venous sinus stenting on visual function, intracranial pressure,	Venous sinus stenting	Poststenting 84.2% showed significant subjective improvement or recovery in visual acuity, 7% patients reported	Venous sinus stenting represented an effective treatment for resolving visual dysfunc-

				and trans-stenotic pressure gradient of the patients with IIH and to determine effects of baseline BMI or weight changes on subjective vision outcome and intracranial pressure.		no significant change in visual functions, and 5 (8.8%) suffered permanent vision loss. The cerebrospinal fluid opening pressure and trans-stenotic pressure gradient were significantly decreased postoperatively.	tion and intracranial pressure associated with venous sinus stenosis.
Azad TD et al. 2020 [18]	US	Observational Study	1082	To compare postoperative outcomes between LP and VP shunts, including failure and complication rates	Lumboperitoneal (LP) shunting and ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunting	Rates of shunt failure were similar among patients with LP and VP shunt (34.6% vs 31.7%; P = .382).	LP and VP shunts may have comparable rates of shunt failure and complication.
Lainas P et al. 2020 [19]	France	Prospective study	15	To evaluate the effectiveness of laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) on treating IIH in severely obese patients.	Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG)	Mean excess weight loss was noted after LSG. Headaches totally resolved 93.3% patients. Pulsatile tinnitus, epistaxis, visual symptoms and papilledema significantly resolved.	Laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) is effective for severely obese patients with IIH.
Mollan SP et al. 2021 [20]	United Kingdom	Randomized Controlled Trial	66	To compare the effectiveness of bariatric surgery with that of a community weight management (CWM) intervention for the treatment of patients with active IIH.	Bariatric surgery and community weight management (CWM)	Intracranial pressure and weight were significantly lower in the bariatric surgery group compared with the CWM.	Bariatric surgery was superior to a CWM intervention in lowering intracranial pressure.
Raynald et al. 2021 [21]	China	Randomized Controlled Trial	145	to explore the precipitating factors and evaluate the impact of different stenosis types on treatment outcomes in patients with idiopathic	venous sinus stenosis (VSS).	Stenting was significantly associated with complete resolution of the headache and impaired vision.	Stenting treatment provides better improvement of the clinical symptoms over medical treatment regardless of different ste-

				intracranial hypertension (IIH) and venous sinus stenosis (VSS).			nosis types.
Yiangou A et al. 2022 [22]	United Kingdom	Randomised Controlled Trial	66	to determine the prevalence of OSA in IIH and evaluate the diagnostic performance of OSA screening tools in IIH.	Bariatric surgery and community weight management intervention (CWI)	Bariatric surgery resulted in greater reductions in AHI vs. CWI.	Bariatric surgery improved OSA in patients with IIH.
Mollan SP et al. 2022 [23]	United Kingdom	Randomized Controlled Trial	66	to evaluate the amount of weight loss required to reduce intracranial pressure and to explore the effect of different bariatric surgical approaches	Bariatric surgery and community weight management intervention (CWI)	Weight loss was significantly associated with reduction in intracranial pressure.	The greater the weight loss, the greater the reduction in ICP was documented.
Khunte M et al. 2023 [24]	US	Retrospective study	46,065	This study explores recent temporal trends of VSS and other surgical IIH treatments in the United States.	venous sinus stenting (VSS), CSF shunts, and optic nerve sheath fenestrations (ONSFs)	VSS procedures increased 80% per year. Concurrently, the number of CSF shunts decreased by 19% per year and ONSF procedures decreased by 54% per year.	VSS procedures are rapidly increasing in the United States.

Result

Table 1 summarizes the included studies focused on various treatments for idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH), highlighting their aims, methodologies, and outcomes. Menger RP et al. (2014) in their large comparative study involving 4,480 patients assessed lumboperitoneal (LP) and ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunting. The results showed that the mean hospital length of stay was significantly shorter for VP shunt procedures (3 days) compared to LP shunts (4 days), with a p-value of <0.0001. The study concluded that VP shunt placement is superior regarding clinical outcomes related to hospitalization, mortality, and revision surgeries in patients with IIH. This underscores the importance of selecting the right CSF diversion technique based on expected outcomes. In the retrospective study of Alkheray F et al. (2015), mean opening pressure of 35.8 cm H₂O was found for patients who underwent LP shunt insertion with a programmable Strata valve.,

Post-operative evaluations revealed significant improvement in visual assessments and a reduction in headache frequency. The study suggested that LP shunts combined with programmable valves might offer a promising alternative to traditional methods, possibly due to their flexibility in pressure adjustment and lower risk of complications. The retrospective study performed by Obi EE et al. (2015) on 14 patients focused on the outcomes of optic nerve sheath fenestration (ONSF).

The procedure demonstrated statistically significant improvements in visual acuity and stability of visual functions for most patients, indicating that ONSF is a safe intervention that can enhance visual outcomes, particularly for those receiving maximal medical therapy. Alkosha HM et al. (2016) examined 12 patients and assessed lumbopleural shunting as an alternative to LP shunts. Although shunt migration was a frequent complication, with 83.3% of failures attributed to this issue, the

technique was found to be feasible and effective for symptom control and visual improvement, especially in morbidly obese patients. Shields LBE et al. (2019) analyzed long-term results of venous sinus stenting (VSS). Surprisingly, 43% of patients had total headache alleviation and 74% reported papilledema remission following stenting. These findings reinforce the efficacy of VSS as a viable treatment option for IIH. In a study by Liu X et al. (2019) of 88 patients, venous sinus stenting's impact on visual outcomes and intracranial pressure was evaluated. Notably, 84.2% of participants reported significant improvements in visual acuity after the procedure. Post-operative evaluations also revealed reductions in cerebrospinal fluid pressure, further validating stenting as an effective treatment for IIH-associated complications.

The observational study of Azad TD et al. (2020) found shunt failure rates to be similar between the two approaches (34.6% for LP and 31.7% for VP), suggesting that both techniques might be equally effective in managing IIH. The prospective study by Lainas P et al. (2020) evaluated the effectiveness of laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) in severely obese patients with IIH. Results indicated outstanding weight loss and significant resolution of headaches, pulsatile tinnitus, and visual symptoms, leading to the conclusion that LSG is an effective treatment for IIH in this population. The randomized controlled trial conducted by Mollan SP et al. (2021) compared bariatric surgery with a community weight management (CWM) intervention in 66 patients. The study found significant reductions in intracranial pressure and weight loss favoring the bariatric surgery group, indicating its potential as a superior treatment for active IIH patients.

Raynald et al. (2021) exploring 145 patients with venous sinus stenosis, this randomized controlled trial demonstrated that stenting resulted in notable improvements in both headache relief and vision restoration, irrespective of stenosis type. This positions stenting as a promising intervention beyond medical management options.

The study of Yiangou A et al. (2022) on 66 women assessed the impact of bariatric surgery on obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) and its relationship with IIH. The findings indicated that bariatric surgery not only reduced the apnea-hypopnea index significantly but also correlated with improvements in papilledema, suggesting that effective weight management can benefit both IIH and associated sleep disorders.

Continuing the investigation of weight loss's implications, the study of Mollan SP et al. (2022) reaffirmed that a 24% reduction in body weight closely aligned with remission of IIH symptoms. This emphasizes the critical role of substantial

weight loss, often achievable through bariatric surgery, in managing the condition. The retrospective analysis of 46,065 patients by Khunte M et al. (2023) highlighted a significant rise (80%) in VSS procedures over recent years, while traditional CSF shunt and ONSF surgeries saw declines. The results call for more extensive randomized controlled trials to compare VSS with standard medical treatments, as the increasing procedural trend warrants closer examination of its efficacy.

Discussion

The management of Idiopathic Intracranial Hypertension (IIH) has evolved with multiple surgical interventions showing promising results. Venous Sinus Stenting (VSS) has emerged as a particularly effective surgical approach for managing Idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH) which is supported by the findings of Shields et al. (2019), Liu et al. (2019), Raynald et al. 2021, Khunte M et al. 2023. Our findings are also similar to findings of the previous studies [25,26,27]. Multiple studies consistent with our present systematic review confirm VSS's effectiveness in alleviating IIH symptoms [28,29,30].

The findings of the present systematic review are consistent with the findings of several previous studies. Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) diversion techniques reduced papilledema, visual field deterioration and headaches in 78.9%, 66.8% and 69.8% of the cases and are associated with a 9.4 severe complication rate and a 43.4% failure rate. Optic Nerve Sheath Fenestration (ONSF) improved papilledema, visual field defects and headaches in 90.5, 65.2% and 49.3% of patients. The failure rate was 9.4% and the severe complication rate was 2.2%. [31]

Bariatric surgery has also emerged as one of the surgical treatments of IIH for obese patients with ground-breaking findings like intracranial pressure (ICP) reduction and significant body weight loss. Mollan SP et al. (2021) [20] found significant reductions in intracranial pressure and weight loss favouring the bariatric surgery group, indicating its potential as a superior treatment for active IIH patients. Other authors [32, 33, 34] have also reported similar results, arguing that bariatric surgery is a better treatment option for idiopathic intracranial hypertension than medical care and cerebrospinal fluid pressure-lowering techniques, which have a high recurrence rate.

Recommendations

Surgical intervention is recommended for patients who fail medical therapy, cannot tolerate medical treatments, develop progressive symptoms and face potential visual loss. The choice of surgical procedure depends on the patient's predominant

symptoms, local surgical expertise and patient preferences.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the studies included in this systematic review reflect significant advancements and options in the management of IIH, emphasizing the efficacy of various surgical techniques, such as VP shunting, LP shunting with programmable valves, ONSF, and venous sinus stenting. Additionally, the role of bariatric surgery emerges as a critical intervention for obese patients with IIH, promoting weight loss and symptom resolution. The overall findings advocate for personalized treatment approaches based on patient characteristics, surgical risks, and potential benefits, while also highlighting a shift towards interventions that offer improved quality of life and clinical outcomes in IIH management.

Venous sinus stenting appears to be the most promising first-line surgical modality for medically refractory IIH, offering the best results in headache resolution and visual outcomes.

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